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JOURNAL OF THE INDIAN ECONOMIC ASSOCIATION

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GREEN AND INCLUSIVE GROWTH FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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- Enhanced Prosperity and Growing Social Equity Within the Contours of a Finite and Fragile Planet
- Green Growth and Sustainable Development Goals

The Indian Economic Journal

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The Econometric Analysis of Health Expenditure Inflow with Economic Growth in India

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IEA

Ashok Bhukta¹
Sudhakar Patra²

Abstract

There is an association of health expenditure inflow with economic performance. Health expenditure inflow can result in better provision of services opportunities, which can strengthen health expenditure inflow and improve productivity, thereby contributing to economic performance. It is therefore important to assess the phenomenon of high economic growth in a country. Based on economic growth the study empirically examines the linkage of health expenditure inflow with economic growth. The proxy variables for economic growth are taken such as GDP using data collected from a secondary source like World Bank Data (WBD). The model, Vector Error Correction Model has been used to find the long-run and short-run causality among the variables where the Johansen Co-integration test for the long-run causality and short-run causality Wald test has been applied. Wald tests to conclude the objective of the study. The data span for the study is from 2000 to 2021. Wald tests show the bidirectional causal relationship in all variables. Therefore, this study concludes by recommending, the strategy to improve health expenditure inflow to improve the GDP. The findings from the Johansen Co-integration test indicated that there exists a long-run relationship between India's health expenditure and GDP. Furthermore, the Granger causality test detected bi-directional causality from GDP to health expenditure. These results were further confirmed by findings from the impulse response function. This means that India represents an example of a developing economy where the size of health expenditure expands in the process of economic transformation. And also the VECM model has been used.

Key Words: GDP, Private Health expenditure, ADF, Public Health expenditure, VECM

Introduction

The health expenditure estimates have been prepared by the World Health Organization under the framework of the System of Health Accounts 2011. Public expenditure on health from domestic sources as a share of the economy as measured by GDP (Grover, 2015). Share of current health expenditures funded from domestic private sources. Domestic private sources include funds from households, corporations and non-profit organizations. Such expenditures can be either prepaid to voluntary health insurance or paid directly to Health

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providers. Share of current health expenditures funded from external sources (Behera D. K., 2017). External sources compose of direct foreign transfers and foreign transfers distributed by the government encompassing all financial inflows into the national health system from outside the country (Maurya & Singh, 2017). External sources either flow through the government scheme or are channelled through non-governmental organizations or other schemes (Verma & Usmani, 2019).

Significance of the Study

There are a lot of empirical studies which study the relationship between Health Expenditure and Economic growth in India. But there is still an unfulfilled gap related to the issue and impact of government expenditure on economic growth in India (Yun & Yusoff, 2015). By conducting this study it is expected that this gap will be covered. This study is to analyse the impact of government expenditure on Health and Economic growth in India covering the period from 2000 to 2021. Then this study will fulfil the objectives of the Econometric Analysis of Health Expenditure Inflow with Economic Growth in India (Cosimo Magazzino, 2011).

Hypotheses of the Study

Hypothesis-1, Null hypotheses-H₀: Public Health Expenditure does not Granger Cause Economic Growth.

Alternative hypotheses-H₁: Public Health Expenditure does Granger Cause Economic Growth.

Hypotheses-2, Null hypothesis-H₀: Economic Growth does not Granger Cause Public Health Expenditure.

Alternative hypotheses-H₁: Economic Growth does Granger Cause Public Health Expenditure.

Methodology

In this study, three variables are taken into the consideration. They are GDP (Y) as a dependent variable, Public Health Expenditure (X₁) and Private Health Expenditure (X₂) as independent variables. In the evaluation process, different analysis is performed to check the effect of total public health expenditure on economic growth and the effect of total private health expenditure on economic growth (Asif & Sultan, 2013). The data in an actual number of all three variables in average are taken to check the relationship between the variables. The data of these four variables from 2000 to 2021 are used and have been collected from World Bank data sources. The data are analyzed to determine the causality between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India as well as private health expenditure and Economic Growth (GDP) of India (Pradhan J. & Behera S., 2020). Before analyzing the causal relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth data has been transformed into natural logarithms, and then the possible existence of unit roots in the data is examined.

The number of lagged differences included is determined by the Schwarz Information Criterion and Akaike Information Criteria. Further, proceed with the VAR lag order selection criteria to choose the best lag length for the VAR time series model to examine the Granger Causality test for all the series performed (Khan et al., 2016). Johansen's co-integration test is also applied to test for co-integration. The basic empirical investigation has two purposes. The first one is to examine the long-run relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth while the second is to examine the short-run dynamic causal relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth (Mehta, 2017). The basic testing procedure requires three steps. The first step is to test whether the variables contain a unit root to confirm the stationarity of each variable. This is done by the use of the Johansen co-integration test. Finally, in the last step, if all variables are integrated of the same order and co-integrated then short-run and long-run causality tests can be computed using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) method suggested by Engle and Granger (Magazzino &

Mele, 2012). Summarising, step one is the Unit Root Test, step two is Lag Selection, step three is the Co-integration test, and the last step is VECM.

Present Status of Health Expenditure inflow with GDP in India

The actual number of the three variables like Total Public Health Expenditure, Private Health Expenditure and Economic Growth Rate (World Bank Database, 2021) in India from 2000 to 2021 has been depicted. It is visible that all three variables are in the increasing number that is the PHE. Since the level data of independent variables are non-stationary of the public and private health expenditure, so the third and second and third column shows the 1st difference between Public and private health expenditure.

Checking the Stationarity of the variables

Figure-1: Unit root test of Public health expenditure (Level)

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

The above figure that is figure-1 shows the inconsistency of both mean and variance over time. But for further analysis, there should have a couple of criteria like there should have a constant mean over time and also constant variance over time and should have no seasonal component. Here the mean starts rather low and seems to be going up to infinity, so for that reason alone we probably say that that is not stationary.

Table-1: Result of Stationarity of X₁ Variable (1st Difference) (Trend and Intercept)

Null Hypothesis: D(Public Health Expenditure,2) has a unit root

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=6) Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.48	0.00
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.36	
5% level	-3.59	
10% level	-3.23	

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

With trend and intercept also this is stationary which is depicted in the above result table.

Table-2: Result of Stationarity of X₂ Variable (in Level) (in Trend and Intercept)

Null Hypothesis: Private Health Expenditure has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend, Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=6)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.14	0.50

Test critical values:	1% level	-4.32
	5% level	-3.58
	10% level	-3.22

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

The above result table indicates the series is non-stationary in level with trend and intercept because the p-value is 0.5%.

Figure-2: Unit root test of Private Health Expenditure (in 1st Difference)

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

In this figure-2, it seems to have both mean and variance constant over the period. So it is stationary in process. With trend and intercept also this is stationary which is depicted in the above result table.

Table-3: Panel Unit Root Test Result:

Variables	Level Value (Probability)		1st Difference (Probability)	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept
Public Health Expenditure	0.99	0.62	0.00*	0.00*
Private Health Expenditure	0.97	0.50	0.00*	0.00*

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software, note: * indicates stationary.

Table-3 provides clear information about the level probability values of the two independent variables which are higher than 0.05 both in intercept and trend & intercept. It shows that these variables have unit roots. Since the Null hypothesis is the series is having unit-roots. Therefore, the first-order difference between these variables is taken into the consideration. And it is seen that both variables are stationary at 1st difference.

Lag Selection

Table-4: Result of VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: X1 X2 Y, Exogenous variables: C
 , Sample: 2000-2021, Included observations: 22

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-272.92	NA	774454.80	22.07	22.22	22.11
1	-193.95	132.66	2895.05	16.48	17.06	16.64

2	-183.82	14.59	2745.71	16.38	17.41	16.67
3	-165.29	22.23	1410.66	15.62	17.09	16.03
4	-133.97	30.07*	287.70*	13.84*	15.73*	14.36*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion
 LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)
 FPE: Final prediction error
 AIC: Akaike information criterion
 SC: Schwarz information criterion
 HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

So here out of all lag selection criteria, all are showing four lags. Hence the majority of cases are showing 4 lags. So here 4 lags are selected. In each criterion except LR, the lower the value better the lag selection principle is there.

VECM (Vector Error Correction Methods):

Already we have the lag selection criteria and co-integration test. Now we will move to Vector Error Correction Criteria. Before proceeding we will check the correlogram of each independent variable for checking the stationary level, though we have already checked the same using the unit root test.

Table-5: Correlogram of D(X₁)

Sample: 2000- 2021
 Included observations: 22

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.130	-0.130	0.5119	0.474
		2	-0.227	-0.248	2.1226	0.346
		3	-0.161	-0.250	2.9719	0.396
		4	0.040	-0.109	3.0263	0.553
		5	-0.273	-0.458	5.6875	0.338
		6	0.249	0.008	7.9984	0.238
		7	0.102	-0.099	8.4035	0.298
		8	-0.024	-0.120	8.4278	0.393
		9	-0.150	-0.152	9.4089	0.400
		10	0.115	-0.077	10.014	0.439
		11	-0.062	-0.061	10.202	0.512
		12	0.142	0.132	11.248	0.508

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Since all p values are more than 5%, the H₀ is accepted, which means the series is stationary. So here the null hypothesis is variable is stationary. But the p-value is less than 5%. Hence H₁ is accepted, that is series is not stationary at level. So we will go for 1st difference.

Table-6: Correlogram of D(X₂)

Sample: 2000-2021
 Included observations: 22

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.074	-0.074	0.1705	0.680
		2	-0.058	-0.064	0.2799	0.869
		3	0.484	0.479	8.1457	0.043
		4	-0.120	-0.082	8.6467	0.071
		5	-0.145	-0.146	9.4106	0.094
		6	0.269	0.037	12.176	0.058
		7	-0.114	-0.019	12.696	0.080
		8	-0.121	-0.010	13.314	0.102
		9	0.024	-0.192	13.339	0.148
		10	-0.094	-0.037	13.755	0.184
		11	-0.165	-0.100	15.097	0.178
		12	-0.072	-0.081	15.368	0.222

Since maximum p values are more than 5%, so the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence series is stationary at 1st difference. So the summary is both independent variables are non-stationary at level, but when I convert into 1st difference, both series are stationary. Hence both are stationary in the same order. That is why I applied for the Co-integration test. Now I will go for VECM Model. So the guideline is if the variables are co-integrated or have long-run association ship then we can run restricted VAR, I.e, the VECM model. But if the variables are not co-Integrated, we cannot use the VECM model rather we shall run unrestricted VAR. So here all three variables are co-integrated, we can go for the VECM model.

Table-7: Co-integration Model

Vector Error Correction Estimates

Sample (adjusted): 2000-2021, Included observations: 22 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

Cointegrating Eq:	Coint. Eq1
Y(-1)	1.00
X1(-1)	-81.95
X2(-1)	-4.18
C	-167.71

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

The Co-integrating Model

$$C(1)*(Y(-1) - 81.95*X_1(-1) - 4.18*X_2(-1) - 167.71) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Table-8: Error Correction model

Error Correction:	D(Y)	D(X1)	D(X2)
Coint. Eq1	0.84	0.01	-0.03
	(1.15)	(0.00)	(0.01)
	[0.73]	[2.10]	[-2.46]
C	119.41	1.23	-2.70
	(131.04)	(0.61)	(1.39)
	[0.91]	[2.00]	[-1.94]
R-squared	0.64	0.92	0.93
Adj. R-squared	0.16	0.82	0.84
Mean dependent	71.22	0.76	1.34
S.D. dependent	80.59	0.82	1.98

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

So here D(Y) is the target variable and the VECM model automatically converts the variables into 1st difference. For example, the variables are coming with D(y), D(x₁) and D(x₂). Furthermore, here each variable is having four lags, according to the lag criteria selection. So here the **target model** is as follows:

$$Y_t = 119.41 - 1.35Y_{t-1} - 1.69Y_{t-2} + 0.23Y_{t-3} + 0.44Y_{t-4} + 116.57X_{1t-1} + 140.77X_{1t-2} - 115.18X_{1t-3} - 18.63X_{1t-4} + 28.56X_{2t-1} + 3.24X_{2t-2} - 10.08X_{2t-3} - 3.80X_{2t-4} + U_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

And the **system equation models** are as follows: **System Equation Models**

$$D(Y) = C(1)*(Y(-1) - 81.95*X_1(-1) - 4.18*X_2(-1) - 167.71) + C(2)*D(Y(-1)) + C(3)*D(Y(-2)) + C(4)*D(Y(-3)) + C(5)*D(Y(-4)) + C(6)*D(X_1(-1)) + C(7)*D(X_1(-2)) + C(8)*D(X_1(-3)) + C(9)*D(X_1(-4)) + C(10)*D(X_2(-1)) + C(11)*D(X_2(-2)) + C(12)*D(X_2(-3)) + C(13)*D(X_2(-4)) + C(14) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

D(Y)= target variable,

$C(1)$ = the coefficient of the co-integrating model and

$C(1)$ is also the Error Correction Term or Speed of adjustment towards equilibrium.

So there are two issues: 1. Long-run causality, 2. Short-run causality

Long-Run Causality:

If this $C(1)$ is negative in sign and significant, then we can say that there is a long-run causality running from X_1 and X_2 to Y . So here the p-value of $C(1)$ is 0.4824 which is more than 5%. This is not significant. Meaning that there is no long-run causality running from Public expenditure and private expenditure to GDP (Asif & Sultan, 2013). And the second issue is as follows.

Short-Run Causality:

Here the coefficients of all the four lags of 1st independent variable which is public health expenditure are $C(6)$, $C(7)$, $C(8)$, and $C(9)$. So if they are zero ($H_0=C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$), it can be said there is no short-run causality running from Public expenditure to GDP. So to check it we will go to the Wald test (Wald Chi-Squared Test).

Wald Test (Wald Chi-Squared Test)

The null hypothesis for the test is some parameter = some value. For example, here study if GDP is affected by public health expenditure. "GDP" would be my parameter. The value could be zero (indicating that GDP is affected by public health expenditure). If the null hypothesis is rejected, it suggests that the variables in question can be removed without much harm to the model fit. That is illustrated as follows:

Table-9: Wald Test: Equation: Wald Chi-Squared Test

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	0.63	(4, 10)	0.65
Chi-square	2.51	4	0.64

Null Hypothesis: $C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$ Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
$C(6)$	116.57	100.46
$C(7)$	140.76	115.18
$C(8)$	-115.17	94.20
$C(9)$	-18.63	50.04

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the p-value is 64.20%, which means the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence $C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$. Therefore, there is no short-run causality running from public health expenditure to GDP.

And the second independent variable, i.e, private health expenditure, which does cause GDP or not. Here is the coefficient of all lags of these variables in $C(10)$, $C(11)$, $C(12)$, and $C(13)$. Again the null hypothesis is $C(10)=C(11)=C(12)=C(13)=0$. Whether this is zero or not I check the Wald test.

Table-10: Wald Test: Equation: Wald Chi-Squared Test

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	0.71	(4, 10)	0.60
Chi-square	2.83	4	0.59

Null Hypothesis: C(10)= C(11)= C(12)= C(13)=0 Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(10)	28.56	31.12
C(11)	3.24	17.17
C(12)	-10.08	21.50
C(13)	-3.80	26.07

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

The p-value is 58.69% which makes the null hypothesis accepted. This means all the coefficients of X2 variables are zero. Therefore, there is no short-run causality from private health expenditure to GDP. Hence, it can be said that no Long-run or short-run causality is running from private health expenditure and public health expenditure to GDP. This means there is no association ship from X1 and X2 to Y variable. So the question is how the model is. It leads to diagnostic checking.

$$D(Y) = C(1)*(Y(-1) - 81.95*X1(-1) - 4.18*X2(-1) - 167.71) + C(2)*D(Y(-1)) + C(3)*D(Y(-2)) + C(4)*D(Y(-3)) + C(5)*D(Y(-4)) + C(6)*D(X1(-1)) + C(7)*D(X1(-2)) + C(8)*D(X1(-3)) + C(9)*D(X1(-4)) + C(10)*D(X2(-1)) + C(11)*D(X2(-2)) + C(12)*D(X2(-3)) + C(13)*D(X2(-4)) + C(14) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Table-11: Least Squares Method

Dependent Variable: D(Y), Method: Least Squares (Gauss-Newton / Marquardt steps)
 Sample (adjusted): 2000-2021, Included observations: 22 after adjustments

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	0.84	1.15	0.73	0.48
C(2)	-1.35	1.29	-1.05	0.32
C(3)	-1.69	1.44	-1.17	0.27
C(4)	0.23	0.86	0.27	0.79
C(5)	0.45	0.62	0.73	0.48
C(6)	116.57	100.46	1.16	0.27
C(7)	140.77	115.18	1.22	0.25
C(8)	-115.18	94.20	-1.22	0.25
C(9)	-18.63	50.04	-0.37	0.72
C(10)	28.56	31.12	0.92	0.38
C(11)	3.24	17.17	0.19	0.85
C(12)	-10.08	21.50	-0.47	0.65
C(13)	-3.80	26.07	-0.15	0.89
C(14)	119.41	131.04	0.91	0.38
R-squared	0.64	Mean dependent var		71.22
Adjusted R-squared	0.16	S.D. dependent var		80.59
Prob(F-statistic)	0.32			

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the R-squared value is more than 60% which is 64%, so the model is a good fit. Again regarding the residuals diagnostic, I further check the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation test.

Table-12: Serial Correlation Test

F-statistic	0.98	Prob. F(2,8)	0.41
Obs*R-squared	4.74	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.09

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the null hypothesis is there is no serial correlation. And the p-value is 9.32%, which is more than 5% making the H_0 accepted. Therefore, in this model no serial correlation in the residuals.

Table-13: Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

(Test Equation: Dependent Variable: RESID^2, Method: Least Squares, Sample: 2000-2021)

F-statistic	0.67	Prob. F(15,8)	0.76
Obs*R-squared	13.34	Prob. Chi-Square(15)	0.58
Scaled explained SS	1.77	Prob. Chi-Square(15)	1.00

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the p-value is more than 5%, i.e., 57.62%, which leads towards accepting the null hypothesis. This means there is no heteroscedasticity in the residuals. Which is desirable in a model.

Figure-3: Normality Test

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the value of Jarque-Bera is 76.78% and the p-value is 68.12% which is more than 5%. Hence we cannot reject H_0 rather we accept the null hypothesis. This means the residual is normally distributed. So overall the model is a good fit.

Estimation and Empirical Analysis of the Results

During the investigation of a long-run relationship among the variables such as **GDP (Y)** as a dependent variable, **Public Health Expenditure (X₁)** and **Private Health Expenditure (X₂)** as independent variables, first of all, the series is tested for stationarity,

since the data used in the present study is time-series in nature. If there is a unit root, the series is non-stationary. The tests of unit roots were performed using Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test. The null hypothesis is that the series has a unit root against the alternative. The result of the unit root test is reported in table-14.

Table-14: Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-272.92	NA	774454.8	22.07	22.22	22.11
1	-193.95	132.66	2895.05	16.48	17.06	16.64
2	-183.82	14.59	2745.71	16.39	17.41	16.67
3	-165.29	22.23	1410.66	15.62	17.09	16.03
4	-133.97	30.07*	287.70*	13.84*	15.04*	14.36*

Source: Computed by Author using E-views (* indicates lag order selected by the criterion, LR: sequentially modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level), FPE: Final prediction error, AIC: Akaike information criterion, SC: Schwarz information criterion, HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion)

So here out of all lag selection criteria, all are showing four lags. Hence, the majority of cases are showing 4 lags. So here 4 lags are selected. In each criterion except LR, the lower the value better the lag selection principle is there.

Johansen's Test of Co-integration

Table-14a: Unrestricted Co-integration (Trace Test)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen Value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.*
None	0.52	29.97	29.80	0.05
At most 1	0.31	10.17	15.49	0.27

Note: The test was performed using E-views

Trace statistics show no Co-integration at a 5 % critical level. Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

The result shows that the variables are non-stationary at level but are stationary at first difference. Hence, the Johansen test for co-integration is applied to find co-integration between **GDP (Y)** as a dependent variable, **Public Health Expenditure (X₁)** and **Private Health Expenditure (X₂)**. Since they are integrated of the same order, thus ensuring the condition to apply Johansen Co-integration, I test the existence of co-integration between these variables. Since the result of VAR analysis is also affected by the number of lag periods, appropriate lag is selected based on Akaike information criteria (AIC) shown in table-14a.

Table-15: Johansen's Test of Co-integration (Maximum Eigen-value Test)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen Value	Maximum Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.*
None	0.52	19.80	21.13	0.07
At most 1	0.31	10.13	14.26	0.20

Note: The test was performed using E-views

Trace statistics show no Co-integration at a 5 % critical level. Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Johansen's Co-integration Analysis

Using Johansen's co-integration relationship, the paper has examined the existence of a long-run relationship between public health expenditure and GDP, and private health expenditure and GDP. The result shows that public health expenditure and private health

expenditure are integrated in a different order (Magazzino & Mele, 2012). Hence, these two variables will not have a Co-integration relationship. The result of Co-integration between per capita domestic income and capita planned expenditure rejects the hypothesis of the existence of a long-run relationship between these two. Thus we may conclude that the growth of planned health expenditure over time the period may have occurred due to other reasons than to increase in per capita income of the country.

Table-16: Panel Causality Analysis Results

The way of the Relationship	Lag	Probability Values	Results
Public Health Expenditure → Economic Growth	1	0.74	Public Health Expenditure does not Cause Economic Growth
	2	0.62	
	3	0.56	
	4	0.42	
Economic Growth → Public Health Expenditure	1	0.04*	Economic Growth is the main cause of Public Health Expenditure
	2	0.00*	
	3	0.00*	
	4	0.00*	
Private Health Expenditure → Economic Growth	1	0.00*	Private Health Expenditure does not cause Economic Growth
	2	0.23	
	3	0.69	
	4	0.51	
Economic Growth → Private Health Expenditure	1	0.00*	Economic Growth is the main of Private Health Expenditure
	2	0.00*	
	3	0.00*	
	4	0.01*	

Source: Computed by Author (* mark indicates significant)

Table-18 shows that there is no causality relationship between public health expenditure to economic growth. The main reason for having all lag values is greater than 0.05. This scenario is also similar concerning the relationship between private health expenditure to economic growth. As a result the null hypothesis which is “no causality relationship” is accepted. Moreover, in the case of private health expenditure to economic growth, the first lag shows a significant probability value that is less than 5% but except first lag the rest four lags are greater than 5%. Hence null hypothesis of “no causality relationship” cannot be rejected.

Regarding economic growth to public health expenditure and private health expenditure, in both these cases, the probabilistic values are less than 5% in the case of all four lags, as the result, showing the significant value leads to rejecting the null hypothesis. So there is a causality relationship between economic growth to both public and private health expenditure. Finally, it can be said that in our country, economic growth leads to higher public health expenditure as well as private health expenditure.

Development relevance in Economic Growth and Health Expenditure

The economy's growth is measured by the change in the volume of its output or the real incomes of its residents. Strengthening health financing is one objective of Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG target 3). The levels and trends of health expenditure data identify key issues such as weaknesses and strengths and areas that need investment, for instance, additional health facilities, better health information systems, or better-trained human resources (Bedir, 2016). Health financing is also critical for reaching universal health coverage (UHC) defined as all people obtaining the quality health services they need without suffering financial hardship (SDG 3).

Conclusion

In this study, we have examined the relationship between Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth for India during the period from 2000 to 2021. This study uses the ADF unit root test, Johansen co-integration and Vector Error Correction techniques to investigate the long-run and short-run causality between Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India. From the above study, it can be concluded that the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root tests show the Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth series become stationary when the first difference is considered. The empirical result reveals that there is no long-run co-integrating relationship between Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India. I found that there is no long-run causality between Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth. But in the short-run unidirectional causality is running from Economic Growth to Government Health Expenditure. It means in the short-run Economic Growth leads to Government Health Expenditure in India.

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